

Effect of denaturants on the speciation of dicarboxylic acids : uranium(VI) complexes of oxalic acid in micellar media

B. B. V. Sailaja, Tesfahun Kebede, G. Nageswara Rao and M. S. Prasada Rao*

Bio-inorganic Chemistry Laboratories, School of Chemistry, Andhra University, Visakhapatnam-530 003, India
E-mail : muvvala_2000@yahoo.com

Manuscript received 17 July 2001, revised 19 December 2001, accepted 9 February 2002

A computer assisted pH-metric investigation has been carried out on the effect of micelles on the complexes of uranium(VI) with oxalic acid. Approximate formation constants have been calculated with the computer program SCPHD utilizing the experimental data obtained by monitoring H^+ ion concentration. The formation constants thus obtained are refined with the computer program MINQUAD75. Selection of the best-fit chemical model is based on the statistical parameters and residual analysis. The major complexes formed are $[UO_2(C_2O_4)_2]^{2-}$, $UO_2(C_2O_4)$ and $[UO_2(C_2O_4)_2OH]^{3-}$. The distribution patterns of the different species with pH show that $[UO_2(C_2O_4)_2]^{2-}$ is the predominant species. Influence of the micelles on the speciation is discussed based on the distribution of the various species in the Stern layer and in bulk solvent. The probable structures of the complexes are also given.

Fatty acids are useful reagents for extraction of uranyl ions and studies on the stabilities of uranyl complexes of ligands containing carboxyl groups are worthwhile in this respect. Uranyl complexes of dicarboxylic acids have been studied extensively^{1,2}. Rajan and Martell^{3,4} correlated the stability constants of their chelates with the acid dissociation constants of the ligand acids. The stabilities of the complexes of different stoichiometry formed by uranium(VI) with phthalic, maleic, oxalic, malonic, succinic and propane-1,2,3-tricarboxylic acids in aqueous solutions have been investigated by potentiometry⁴.

Surfactants in water develop microenvironment by forming micelles. The micelles compartmentalize chemical processes and alter the reaction rates, and shift equilibria primarily by concentrating reactants within the small volume of the micellar pseudophase. The extent of change is a product of the micellar effect on reaction within the micellar pseudophase and the distribution of reactants between the two phases. Therefore, the equilibria involved in the interaction of the dioxouranium(VI) ion with dicarboxylates has been undertaken. The present paper deals with the potentiometric study of the interaction of the uranyl ion with oxalic acid in anionic, cationic and neutral micellar media. The protonation constants of oxalic and malonic acids⁵ and the stability constants of uranyl-malonate systems² in anionic, cationic and neutral micellar media were reported earlier.

Results and Discussion

Complex equilibria :

Based on the earlier reports⁶ on oxalato complexes, the

maximum number of ligands bound to the metal ion is restricted to three. The possible complex species considered in developing different models are MLH, ML, ML(OH), ML(OH)₂, ML₂H₂, ML₂H, ML₂, ML₂(OH), ML₂(OH)₂, ML₃H₂, ML₃H, ML₃(OH) and ML₃(OH)₂. In view of the large number of species, it is not pragmatic to consider all models for refinement process. Hence, the species, are refined based on several thumb rules⁷.

The concentration of ML₃ species is very low in the pH range of study. The low concentration of ML₃ species may be because the oxygen atoms on uranium in uranyl do not favour the formation of ML₃ species. Large standard deviations obtained with the inclusion of the ML₃ species clearly support this supposition. The rejection of ML₃ species in case of malonic acid² was also attributed to the crowding of the ligand group, which is relatively larger. The best-fit models are given in Table 1. Literature⁸ shows that oxalic acid interacts strongly with uranyl ion to form ML₂ complex ($\log \beta_2 = 9.1 \pm 0.2$).

Low standard deviations in $\log \beta$ values indicate the precision of these parameters. Small values of sum of squares of residuals (U_{corr}) indicate that the model can represent the experimental data. The deviation of residuals from Gaussian distribution (normal distribution) is reflected by the statistical parameters skewness and kurtosis. Skewness indicates whether the residuals are concentrated to the left or to the right of the mean. Kurtosis indicates the peakedness of the residual curve. For an ideal normal distribution, the values of kurtosis and skewness should be three and zero, respectively. The kurtosis values of most of the systems indicate

Table 1. Best-fit chemical models of UO_2 -oxalic acid equilibria in micellar media

Temp. = 303 K, ionic strength = 0.17 mol dm^{-3}

Surfactant %	$\log \beta_{\text{mlh}}$			pH range	NP	$U_{\text{corr}} \times 10^8$	χ^2	$R \times 10^3$	Skewness	Kurtosis
	110	120	12-1							
0.0	3.65(9)	9.14(8)	2.58(1)	1.6-7.0	198	5.13	38.63	14.1	0.86	6.01
SLS (% w/v)										
0.5	4.40(4)	9.85(1)	3.18(1)	1.6-7.0	195	1.45	33.74	7.82	-1.03	8.82
1.0	5.55(4)	9.26(3)	2.80(4)	1.4-7.0	203	3.24	50.12	10.7	-0.74	5.46
1.5	5.45(9)	10.29(5)	-	1.3-7.0	227	26.62	199.72	18.12	-3.48	18.83
2.0	5.43(2)	9.53(2)	-	2.0-7.0	226	32.48	14.72	16.54	-1.09	2.93
TX-100 (% v/v)										
0.5	4.93(4)	9.21(2)	2.15(5)	1.5-7.0	235	2.33	70.39	6.3	0.01	4.85
1.0	5.11(7)	9.66(4)	2.78(5)	1.5-7.0	245	1.95	41.74	5.55	-0.55	3.29
1.5	4.96(5)	9.71(2)	2.66(5)	1.5-7.0	237	1.55	23.82	5.06	-0.99	6.59
2.0	5.69(3)	9.87(2)	3.06(2)	1.5-7.0	236	2.45	79.25	6.47	-1.46	5.67
2.5	4.69(2)	9.92(4)	2.86(9)	1.5-7.0	245	6.53	28.90	1.0	-0.55	2.83
CTAB (% w/v)										
0.5	5.21(7)	9.36(5)	2.56(6)	1.6-7.0	216	1.54	58.37	5.6	-1.01	9.93
1.0	4.61(7)	9.44(5)	2.31(6)	1.6-7.0	192	2.73	43.22	8.12	0.07	4.76
1.5	4.99(6)	9.59(2)	2.23(9)	1.6-7.0	225	3.43	40.63	7.8	-1.17	6.19
2.0	5.80(1)	9.83(1)	2.96(1)	1.6-7.0	223	0.89	33.03	3.98	-0.23	3.23
2.5	4.51(2)	9.94(3)	3.05(8)	1.6-7.0	234	5.02	63.93	9.04	-0.07	2.67

Table 2. Effect of surfactant on the pH at which maximum concentration of the species is observed for the UO_2 -oxalic acid system

Surfactant	pH (%concentration of species)		
	110	120	12-1
0.0	1.66 (56.11)	5.29 (99.43)	6.76 (58.31)
CTAB (% w/v)			
0.5	1.61 (56.83)	4.62 (96.69)	6.73 (40.27)
1.0	1.66 (30.41)	5.35 (96.50)	6.96 (42.42)
1.5	1.68 (43.89)	5.29 (95.65)	6.97 (30.14)
2.0	1.58 (78.02)	4.62 (95.26)	6.97 (56.31)
2.5	1.56 (46.51)	4.76 (98.32)	6.90 (50.15)
TX (% v/v)			
0.5	1.69 (53.71)	5.36 (94.53)	6.97 (45.43)
1.0	1.55 (51.14)	5.04 (95.54)	6.94 (55.83)
1.5	1.60 (38.95)	5.31 (95.89)	6.93 (44.14)
2.0	1.54 (67.41)	4.78 (95.68)	6.99 (62.90)
2.5	1.55 (21.66)	5.32 (95.84)	6.94 (43.57)
SLS (% w/v)			
0.5	1.76 (51.91)	4.36 (99.26)	6.88 (65.26)
1.0	1.67 (84.93)	4.72 (89.41)	6.72 (66.12)
1.5	1.76 (51.00)	6.50 (98.98)	-
2.0	1.75 (55.00)	5.54 (96.52)	-

that the residuals form platykurtic pattern. The values of skewness between -3.48 and 0.07 evince that the residuals of many systems form a part of normal distribution; hence, least-squares method can be applied to the present data. The sufficiency of the model is further evident from the low crystallographic R value.

Distribution diagrams :

Oxalic acid has two dissociable carboxylate protons. The

distribution of LH_2 and LH^- species of oxalic acid in micellar media⁵ reveals that LH_2 species is predominant at low pH. As the pH increases, its concentration decreases exponentially and becomes almost zero at around pH 5. The concentration of LH_2 species is almost insignificant compared to that of LH^- in the pH range of present investigation for uranium(VI)-oxalato complexes, and this limits the probable metal-ligand species to be ML , ML_2^{2-} , ML_3^{4-} and

Fig. 1. Distribution diagram of uranyl-oxalate systems in 1% SLS.

to some extent the hydroxylated species, ML_2OH^{3-} . The species that are found to exist, however, are ML , ML_2^{2-} and ML_2OH^{3-} .

The distribution of these species of a typical system is given in Fig. 1, which indicates that the unprotonated species (ML and ML_2) are predominant compared to hydroxylated one. Since the LH^- species is predominant in the pH range 1.5–5.0, the plausible metal ligand equilibria are

Literature⁹ shows that uranyl ion (which has a linear structure) has conventionally been assumed to be the centre of the complex, as it does not take part in the inner-sphere substitution reactions and remains unchanged. Besides, uranyl ion exhibits coordination number six. Based on these facts the structures of uranyl-oxalate complexes can be proposed as given in Fig. 2.

Effect of micelles :

For micelle catalyzed bimolecular reactions, the observed rate constants generally go through maxima with increasing concentration of surfactant¹⁰. These maxima arise because higher surfactant concentration increases the concentration of micelle and therefore the amount of reactants in the micellar pseudophase. In micelle catalyzed reactions complex formation occurs in the Stern layer. The species with lower charge is stabilized in the micellar pseudophase; hence neutral complexes will be favored. Micelles separate non-polar molecules from others by encapsulating them in hydrophobic cavity. Hydrophilic ligands will distribute between the micellar surface and bulk water leaving less of the ligand available in the surface region of the micellar for reaction, hence $\log K$ may decrease. Increased concentration of

Fig. 2. Probable structures of uranyl-oxalate chelates.

micellized surfactant leads to the distribution of the reactants over a large amount of micelles¹¹. It leads to a dilution of reactants in the micellar pseudophase and decreases the observed stability constant. The decreasing trend observed in the stability constants of the species may be attributed to the dilution effect.

SLS micelles bind the metal ions electrostatically to the negatively charged micellar surface and decrease the stability constants. On the other hand, positively charged surfactants (like CTAB) decrease the stabilities of the species, probably due to the retention of active ligands such as (LH^-) in the Stern layer while the metal ions are thrown into the bulk solvent. In addition, the metal complexes formed are stabilized by the cationic micelles because the complex ions have negative charges. However, aqueous solutions of CTAB have shown complex behavior with respect to a number of micellar properties, especially when additives like electrolytes and different organic compounds

are present¹². In case of neutral surfactants such as TX, it has been demonstrated that water-insoluble metal chelates can be solubilized with a micellar solution of the non-ionic surfactant. But the decreasing trend of stabilities of uranyl-oxalate complexes is due to destabilization of charged species by TX.

On the basis of the above discussion, it can be concluded that the observed trends are cumulative effects of many factors associated with the nature of the micelles, metal, ligand and complexes formed. This is also reflected in the maximum concentration of the species and the pH of maximum concentration (Table 2).

Experimental

Solutions of uranyl nitrate and oxalic acid (AnalaR) were prepared in triple-distilled water. Aqueous solutions of sodium lauryl sulfate (SLS) (Qualigen), cetyltrimethylammonium bromide (CTAB) (B.D.H.) and Triton X-100 (TX) (E. Merck) were prepared in triple-distilled water.

Alkalimetric titrations were carried out in the medium containing varying compositions of SLS (0.5–2.0%, w/v), CTAB (0.5–2.5%, w/v) and TX (0.5–2.5%, v/v) maintaining an ionic strength of 0.17 mol dm⁻³ with sodium chloride at 303 ± 0.05 K. A Systronics pH meter was used. The glass electrode was equilibrated in a well stirred micellar solution containing inert electrolyte. The effects of variations in asymmetry, liquid junction potential, activity coefficient, sodium ion error and/or dissolved carbon dioxide on the response of glass electrode were taken into account in the form of correction factor (log *F*). It was computed from the simulated acid-base titration data (PHCi) calculated by SCPHD program¹³ for each of the solvent compositions. A correction¹⁴ was applied to the pH meter dial reading to account for the solvent effect on pH. Strong acid was titrated with alkali at regular intervals to check whether complete equilibration was achieved. The calomel electrode was refilled with micellar solution (only TX and CTAB but not SLS since it forms precipitate with KCl) of equivalent composition as that of the titrand. In each titration, the titrand consisted of mineral acid (HClO₄ in case of SLS and TX and HCl in case of CTAB because the latter forms precipitate with HClO₄) of approximately 1 mmol in a total volume of 50 cm³. Titrations with different ratios (1 : 3 and 1 : 5) of metal-to-ligand were carried out with 0.2 mol dm⁻³ sodium hydroxide.

The best-fit chemical models consisting of stoichiometric coefficients and logarithm of stability constants were arrived at using computer program MINIQUAD75¹⁵. Some heuristics⁷ were followed in the refinement of stability constants.

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